

Don't get frustrated . . . OK!

∅ Pali to English : vinipāṭeti
∅ English to Pali : viphalīkaroti; vyāhanati

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Abstract

Frustration, ∅ Pali to English : vinipāṭeti, ∅ English to Pali : viphalīkaroti; vyāhanati, is part and parcel of life. However, HOW to deal with it is in your hands. Events might happen and people will do things to wreck havoc in the course of action, when your line of work is genuine. None the less, it is imperative that one DOES NOT get frustrated! *See frustration as frustration! The frustration has arisen in the mind. DO NOT fight it out and wage another war in your mind! Acknowledge that frustration has happened! Let it rise, reach a peak and fall/subside in its due course. In the stillness of awareness, watch the flow of frustration! Once that mind is clean of the waters of frustration, insight will dawn as to what to NEXT to do, in a constructive manner, also DO the RIGHT thing, that is beneficial to you and beneficial for others in the long run! That RIGHT thing, even the insight of it will be natural thing to do, in alignment with the flow of Mother Nature . . . Don't get frustrated . . . OK!*

In these few words below, have shared some personal experiences and how i have drilled through in my life also, and tried to convey some little knowledge pictorially! May be, in day to day life or on the journey into the realms of the absolute truth! If it helps fine . . . else drop it!

Finally, one will find a series of panels, each of whic have this following structure, with ● a picture representing some wisdom or knowledge gained through personal experience in life, which is followed by ● expression of that knowledge or wisdom in a few words!

Keywords: Frustration.

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1 Panel # 0 - Etymology

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the link to online Pali dictionary at University of Chicago, -

- **Vinipāṭeti** [vi+nipāṭeti] to bring to ruin, to destroy, to frustrate Vin i.298; J vi.71; VvA 208.

Also, from the English-Pali dictionary by Buddhadatta (1989), one finds -

- **frustrate** : (v.t.) viphalīkaroti; vyāhanati. (pp.) viphalīkata; vyāhata

2 Panel # 1 - It has been heard . . . Ananda, once even after serving Siddharta long, in his last life . . .

out of doubt on the Buddha himself, approached the Buddha separately and asked - *Are you hiding something which we don't know off? Some knowledge that we don't know off?*

The Buddha said - *come with me to the forest!*

In the forest, the Buddha picked up a few leaves in his joined palms and said - *Ananda, do you see these leaves in my joined palms? This is what i can show you and this much is, what you can see in this life time! This forest is like a ocean which only i have seen and known. You don't have it in you in the current life to grasp everything!*

From that day, Ananda never questioned Buddha on anything, knowing his own incapability, of that life time and started to work on himself slowly and steadily . . .

Figure 1: The peak of the mountain called Nirvana!

3 Panel # 2 - First acknowledge the state of your own being!

First acknowledge the state of your own being! The current situation or the configuration of the cosmos in time and space that you are in NOW! Know that nothing is permanent . . .

NEITHER accept, NOR reject, JUST ACKNOWLEDGE the situation and your state AS IT IS (i.e yatha-bhuta).

Once the acknowledgement has happened in your own heart and mind, *see what NEXT NEEDS to be done! The RIGHT thing has to be DONE! HOWEVER tough . . . Just HAMMER out the things . . . slowly and steadily in life, day by day! One day at a time . . .*

Just HAMMER it out, slowly and steadily! As the iron smith hammers and straightens an iron rod!

Just do it . . .

Figure 1, depicts the stage of life, one is in . . .

Figure 2: Rest in peace, either below or above!

4 Panel # 3 - Rest in peace!

How about, **INSTEAD** of **FIGHTING** whole life and **THEN** lying in peace in the graveyard, **YOU SIT** and **MEDITATE DAILY** and find some peace within?

Is this ACCEPTABLE to you . . .

Figure 2, depicts the stage in which you want to be peaceful . . .

DON'T GET FRUSTRATED . . . OK!

Figure 3: Postures which you might want to try for yourself and find ABSOLUTE comfort!

5 Panel # 4 - Ways to meditate . . .

See which posture you are MOST comfortable in!

FEEL FREE to choose any, that is in the menu here . . .

It is all for you only!

Figure 3, depicts the postures one wants to try for meditation . . .

Figure 4: Long long long . . . journey!

6 Panel # 5 - It is a long journey . . .

A journey spread over many life times in Mother Nature!

Just acknowledge and accept it!

Figure 4, depicts the long journey spread over many life times . . .

Figure 5: I better than you, and that's it . . . you already lost a chance, may be to learn something!

7 Panel # 6 - ME somebody and YOU nobody . . .

ME somebody and YOU nobody will ruin everyone's life . . .

Value everyone's life . . . however small!

They are a part of existence!

Figure 5, depicts the attitude that most of us have in life . . .

Figure 6: Oooh! I am powerful, BOW DOWN TO ME ONLY, and who are you . . . JUST NOTHING! YOU ARE NOTHING in front of ME . . . ME, ME, ME!

8 Panel # 7 - Man! i am powerful . . .

ALL that MIGHTY ARROGANCE OF your GUN or GOD's POWER will VAPORISE in THIN AIR, when these little one's will give you the LOVE of their KISS . . .

- **Anecdote #1** - Was myself once KISSED in the FOOT by this little one and AFTER the KISS, the SENSATION of the KISS INTENSIFIED in LEAPs and BOUNDs with excruciating pain for 5 hours at a stretch! WHAT PROFOUND LOVE it is from these little ones . . . FORGET the KISS of your LOVED ONEs! These are the real deal!
- **Anecdote #2** - Once, in the campus of UNESCO Mahabodhi Temple, Bodh Gaya, Bihar, India, i sat under a tree (NOT the Bodhi Tree) and then, started RUNNING all the SECURITY PERSONALs WITH SOPHISTICATED modern days weapons, AS IF SCATTERED in THIN AIR as DRY LEAVES in a STORM, when a swarm of bees came down from the trees TO POUNCE on each one! Someone had PELTED a bee hive, up in some tree, in the Mahabodhi campus!

Figure 6, depicts the attitude of megalomaniacs who might have acquired something in life and have started to show their colors after acquiring something, whatever it might be . . .

Figure 7: From the MONKEY mind to SILENT mind : a tough estimation

9 Panel # 8 - From the MONKEY mind to SILENT mind : a tough estimation

FIRST - *acknowledge the MONKEY MIND you have!*

There is NO SHAME in acknowledging! BE SHAMELESS . . . no?

Acknowledge - *this mind of mine is like a MONKEY and i have lived my life like a MONKEY!
How troublesome i have been in life to myself and IN FRONT of others, wherever i go!*

Then **start practicing ANAPANA meditation!** Have given a way to do anapana on my webpage @ [link to Anapana process](#).

To further assist you, here are a few words of the Buddha, in the Mahavagga (The great chapter), Nalaka Sutta (Number 11), in the Sutta-Nipata of Khuddakanikāya (Minor Collection) -

- **Pali** : *Uccāvacā niccharanti, Dāye aggisikhūpamā;*
- **English** : Many different things come up, like tongues of fire in a forest.
- **Pali** : *Moneyyam te upaññissam, Khuradhārūpamo bhava;*
- **English** : To learn the true wisdom regarding the use of the body as an instrument of action . . . like walking on a razor sharp blade, cultivate;

- **Pali** : (*iti bhagavā*)
- **English** : So said the Buddha
- **Pali** : *Jivhāya tālumāhacca,*
- **English** : With the tongue pressed to the roof of your mouth,
- **Pali** : *Udare saññato siyā.*
- **English** : have a say over your stomach and restrain it!
- **Pali** : *Alīnacitto ca siyā, Na cāpi bahu cintaye; Nirāmagandho asito, Brahmacariyaparāyaṇo.*
- **English** : DO NOT be sluggish in mind, nor overthink much. Be free of stench and be unattached, and be committed to the spiritual life.

Figure 7, depicts that this estimation of transforming that MONKEY mind of yours into SILENT mind, is an extremely tough process. And the Buddha gave the Anapana process for it!

DON'T GET FRUSTRATED . . . OK!

Figure 8: Sit still and be . . .

10 Panel # 9 - To meditate or do anapana . . .

To meditate or do anapana . . . *FOLLOW these 4 words, for the rest of your life . . . SIT STILL & BE!*

Figure 8, just depicts that which you might want to do, during your free time . . .

Figure 9: The tongue - a sharp knife!

11 Panel # 10 - The tongue is like a sharp knife, kills without drawing blood . . .

NOW THEN, true it is that you SHOOT OFF arrows from that LOUSY MOUTH of yours . . . from which you eat also!

You EAT anything and FIRE anything, LIKE an UNCONTROLLED LOOSE CANON, wherever you go!

Just ask from your heart, if this is true or not?

NOW, if you have this problem, then here is a solution for you - ROLL that tongue of yours and stick it to the palate and practice this day by day!

You will know after practice, why this has been said so . . . **As the Buddha said - ehipassiko or come and see!** Figure 9, just depicts that sharp tongue of yours that you use . . .

Figure 10: Two coconuts!

12 Panel # 11 - Two types of coconuts!

Accept that you have a COCONUT head and from it emerges strange UNSEEN colours and OUR PLANET becomes so BEAUTIFUL, by your whatever COMES OUT, from that COCONUT head of yours!

Figure 10, just depicts that which you might want to do, during your free time . . .

Figure 11: i want Nirvana!

13 Panel # 12 - Nirvana, Nirvana, Nirvana . . . i want Nirvana!

Nirvana, Nirvana, Nirvana . . . i want Nirvana!

JUST STOP CHANTING this! The greater you CHANT this . . . the further you run away in the OPPOSITE direction!

SIT STILL & BE . . . when the configuration of the cosmos in time and space is right, in Mother Nature, Nirvana will happen!

Siddhartha sat in the jungles of Uruvela, in stillness, alone in seclusion and one moment it happened!

It is simple!

SIT STILL & BE . . .

Figure 11, just depicts that running will not lead you to anywhere. Instead sit with a content heart, in the flow of time, things will happen . . .

Figure 12: What is happening in the OTHER's house is MORE important to you that what is happening in YOUR own HOUSE! Right ? ? ?

14 Panel # 13 - What is happening in other's house? The OTHER's house . . . forget about MINE, the OTHER'S house!

STOP THIS for once and all . . .

WHY are you SO INTERESTED in what is COOKING in other's house? WHY?

Something happens in other's house and NOODLEs cooks in your head ? ? ?

You waste your life's time and you waste everyone else's life's time by DISTRIBUTING and FEEDING this COOKED NOODLEs in YOUR HEAD to OTHERs . . .

Figure 12, just depicts that anything that happens in other's house, and everything starts cooking in your little head and all sorts of things your start thinking off . . .

Figure 13: The BOOTLICKER you, who will GO ON asking for this or that with a bottom pit of desires you have!

15 Panel # 14 - You the BOOTLICKER of Almighty, who will GO ON BEGGING . . .

You the BOOTLICKER of Almighty, who will GO ON BEGGING . . .

Oh! GOD! Give me this, Give me that . . .

That BOTTOMLESS PIT of desires and wants of yours . . .

The REAL BEGGAR and BOOTLICKER of Almighty!

Figure 13, just depicts your incessant asking of things, whether you deserve or not; you just keep on asking! . . .

Figure 14: Your dangerous MONKEY mind!

16 Panel # 15 - Your MONKEY mind . . .

Oooh! DONT LOOK for those MONKEYs outside in existence!

LOOK at your own DANGEROUS monkey mind!

Figure 14, depicts you always neglecting the case that your own monkey mind is so dangerous

...

Figure 15: Save water . . .

17 Panel # 16 - Save water, by doing this . . .

Please do this everyday . . .

On the cumulative, we might save a lot which might be needed somewhere else, DYING in THIRST!

Figure 15, depicts how to save the water, daily!

Figure 16: Look at your cunning mind!

18 Panel # 17 - That twisted cunning mind of yours . . .

You see your own **TWISTED** and **CUNNING** mind and what you do with that to others . . .

You forget about what the others are doing!

Come back later. Now, you see your own cunning mind!

Once you start doing this, you will know that you have NO time in your life, EXCEPT watching your OWN CUNNING mind!

IT is SO WONDERFUL! your CUNNING mind and you!

Figure 16, depicts

in your Victory
if others are victorious
then it is
Merit!

Figure 17: Pictorial depiction!

19 Panel # 18 - Merit

MERIT - NOT intentionally, but by your natural spontaneous action, IF others have won . . . then it is truly something!

In the greater good, if your action has brought you and others victory, then it is real merit!

Figure 17, depicts when your victory is victorious for others, also . . .

Oh! Buddha said
this & that,
but i will never beg
for once in life!

Figure 18: Buddha said this, Buddha said that . . .

20 Panel # 19 - Buddha said this, Buddha said that . . .

Majority are this only . . .

Thus said the Buddha - *ehipassiko or come and see!*

Figure 18, depicts your sermons on what the Buddha said, but you will never beg for once in life, as a part of training!

Figure 19: Who WILL RUN . . . ?

21 Panel # 20 - Get over the rut!

Figure 19, depicts

Figure 20: From pariyatti (theory), to patipatti (practice) to pativedha (attainment)!

22 Panel # 21 - From pariyatti (theory), to patipatti (practice) to pativedha (attainment) . . .

Pariyatti or theoretical knowledge - There is a way to read the scriptures that records the teachings of the ancient ones, be it any path. First one meditates. Say you meditated for a 5 days. Then the next two days you pick up a text that you want to acquire knowledge from. After you have read a few pages, then again meditate. In the stillness of awareness and the depths of the meditation the essence of the knowledge written in words might appear in your awareness and your being might absorb that knowledge. This is a long process. **There are 3 stages of acquiring knowledge** in the higher dimensions of truth & the spiritual realm, i.e - (1) **Suta-maya-panna** or knowledge/wisdom acquired by listening. Listening can be through any of the senses. (2) **Cinta-maya-panna** or knowledge/wisdom acquired via mental chewing of the knowledge. As you chew the chewing gum, so also your mind starts chewing the knowledge, yet the knowledge/wisdom is not completely absorbed. (3) Finally, **Bhavana-maya-panna** or knowledge/wisdom is absorbed in your being. That knowledge settles in your heart also, firmly. **One has to continue on this whole life, as one meditates, contemplates and reads, again and again and again and . . .**

So you move from pariyatti (theory), to patipatti (practice) to pativedha (attainment). One has to continue on this whole life, as one meditates, contemplates and reads, again and again and again and . . .

Fools study voraciously to amass as much information as possible, whether it gets digested or not is not the issue, and will vomit it out in front of everyone to show something. Spiritual debates have the characteristics where one party tries to debate with the other and defeat the other party. Not that it is not useful, but whether knowledge has settled in a being is a vastly different matter. It takes long time to grasp the truths from the abstract dimension . . .

Figure 20, depicts

23 Panel # 22 - The Buddha on frustration

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23.1 Saṃyutta Nikāya 52.8, 1. Rahogatavagga (In Private), Salaḷāgārasutta (The Frankincense-Tree Hut)

Venerable Anuruddha, says -

- **Pali** : “Gaṅgā, āvuso, nadī pācīnaninnā pācīnaṇṇā pācīnapabbhārā.. **English** : The Ganges river slants, slopes, and inclines to the east.
- **Pali** : Sā na sukarā pacchāninnā kātuṃ pacchāṇṇā pacchāpabbhārā.. **English** : It’s not easy to make it slant, slope, and incline to the west.
- **Pali** : Yāvadeva ca pana so mahājanakāyo kilamathassa vighātassa bhāgi assā”ti.. **English** : That large crowd will eventually get weary and **frustrated**.”

23.2 Saṃyutta Nikāya 35.92, 9. Channavagga (With Channa), Paṭhamadvayasutta, (A Duality (1st))

- **Pali** : “Dvayaṃ vo, bhikkhave, desessāmi. Taṃ suṇātha.. **English** : “Mendicants, I will teach you a duality. Listen . . .
- **Pali** : Kiñca, bhikkhave, dvayaṃ?. **English** : And what is a duality?
- **Pali** : Cakkhuñceva rūpā ca, sotañceva saddā ca, ghānañceva gandhā ca, jivhā ceva rasā ca, kāyo ceva phoṭṭhabbā ca, mano ceva dhammā ca - **English** : It’s just the eye and sights, the ear and sounds, the nose and smells, the tongue and tastes, the body and touches, and the mind and ideas.
- **Pali** : idaṃ vuccati, bhikkhave, dvayaṃ. **English** : This is called a duality.
- **Pali** : Yo, bhikkhave, evaṃ vadeyya: **English** : Mendicants, suppose someone was to say:
- **Pali** : ’ahametaṃ dvayaṃ paccakkhāya aññaṃ dvayaṃ paññāpessāmi”ti, tassa vācāvattukamevassa.. **English** : ’I’ll reject this duality and describe another duality.’ They’d have no grounds for that,
- **Pali** : Putṭho ca na sampāyeyya.. **English** : they’d be stumped by questions, and, in addition, they’d get **frustrated**.
- **Pali** : Uttariñca vighātaṃ āpajjeyya. Taṃ kissa hetu? **English** : Why is that?
- **Pali** : Yathā taṃ, bhikkhave, avisayasmin”ti.. **English** : Because they’re out of their element.”

23.3 Aṅguttara Nikāya 4.77, 8. Apanṇakavagga (Unfailing), Acinteyyasutta (Unthinkable)

- **Pali** : “Cattārimāni, bhikkhave, acinteyyāni, na cintetabbāni; yāni cinto ummādassa vighātassa bhāgī assa. **English** : ”Mendicants, these four things are unthinkable. They should not be thought about, and anyone who tries to think about them will go mad or get **frustrated**.”
- **Pali** : *Katamāni cattāri?* **English** : What four?
- **Pali** : *Buddhānaṃ, bhikkhave, buddhavisayo acinteyyo, na cintetabbo;* **English** : The topic of the Buddhas . . .
- **Pali** : *yaṃ cinto ummādassa vighātassa bhāgī assa. Jhāyissa, bhikkhave, jhānavisayo acinteyyo, na cintetabbo;* **English** : The topic of one in absorption . . .
- **Pali** : *yaṃ cinto ummādassa vighātassa bhāgī assa. Kammavipāko, bhikkhave, acinteyyo, na cintetabbo;* **English** : The topic of results of deeds or karma . . .
- **Pali** : *yaṃ cinto ummādassa vighātassa bhāgī assa. Lokacintā, bhikkhave, acinteyyā, na cintetabbā;* **English** : Speculation about the world . . .
- **Pali** : *yaṃ cinto ummādassa vighātassa bhāgī assa. Imāni kho, bhikkhave, cattāri acinteyyāni, na cintetabbāni; yāni cinto ummādassa vighātassa bhāgī assā”ti.* **English** : These are the four unthinkable things. They should not be thought about, and anyone who tries to think about them will go mad or get **frustrated**.”

23.4 Saṃyutta Nikāya 20.5, 1. Opammavagga (Similes), Sattisutta (A Spear)

- **Pali** : *Sāvattiyāṃ viharati.* **English** : At Sāvattihī.
- **Pali** : ”Seyyathāpi, bhikkhave, satti tiṇhaphalā. **English** : ”Mendicants, suppose there was a sharp-pointed spear.
- **Pali** : *Atha puriso āgaccheyya:* **English** : And a man came along and thought,
- **Pali** : *’ahaṃ imaṃ sattim tiṇhaphalaṃ pāṇinā vā muṭṭhinā vā paṭileṇissāmi paṭikottissāmi paṭivattessāmi”ti.* **English** : ’With my hand or fist I’ll fold this sharp spear over, crumple it, and bend it back!’
- **Pali** : *Taṃ kiṃ maññatha, bhikkhave,* **English** : What do you think, mendicants ?
- **Pali** : *bhabbo nu kho so puriso amuṃ sattim tiṇhaphalaṃ pāṇinā vā muṭṭhinā vā paṭileṇetum paṭikottetum paṭivattetun”ti ?* **English** : Is that man capable of doing so?”
- **Pali** : ”No hetam, bhante”. ”Taṃ kissa hetu” ? **English** : “No, sir. Why not?
- **Pali** : ”Asu hi, bhante, satti tiṇhaphalā na sukarā pāṇinā vā muṭṭhinā vā paṭileṇetum paṭikottetum paṭivattetum. **English** : Because it’s not easy to fold that sharp spear over, crumple it, and bend it back with the hand or fist.

- **Pali** : *Yāvadeva ca pana so puriso kilamathassa vighātassa bhāgī assā*”ti. **English** : That man will eventually get weary and **frustrated**.”
- **Pali** : *”Evameva kho, bhikkhave, yassa kassaci bhikkhuno mettācetovimutti bhāvitā bahulīkatā yānīkatā vatthukatā anuṭṭhitā paricitā susamāradhā, tassa ce amanusso cittaṃ khipitabbaṃ maññeyya;* **English** : ”In the same way, suppose a mendicant has developed the heart’s release by love, has cultivated it, made it a vehicle and a basis, kept it up, consolidated it, and properly implemented it. Should any non-human think to overthrow their mind,
- **Pali** : *atha kho sveva amanusso kilamathassa vighātassa bhāgī assa.* **English** : they’ll eventually get weary and **frustrated**.
- **Pali** : *Tasmātiha, bhikkhave, evaṃ sikkhitabbaṃ* : **English** : So you should train like this :
- **Pali** : *’mettā no cetovimutti bhāvitā bhavissati bahulīkatā yānīkatā vatthukatā anuṭṭhitā paricitā susamāradhā*’ti. **English** : ’We will develop the heart’s release by love. We’ll cultivate it, make it our vehicle and our basis, keep it up, consolidate it, and properly implement it.’
- **Pali** : *Evañhi vo, bhikkhave, sikkhitabbaṃ*”ti. **English** : That’s how you should train.”

23.5 Majjhima Nikāya 54, Potaliyasutta (With Potaliya the Householder), in Kāmādinavakathā (The Dangers of Sensual Pleasures)

- **Pali** : *”Seyyathāpi, gahapati, kukkuro jighacchādubbalyapareto goghātakasūnaṃ paccupatthito assa.* **English** : “Householder, suppose a dog weak with hunger was hanging around a butcher’s shop.
- **Pali** : *Tameṇaṃ dakkho goghātako vā goghātakantevāsī vā aṭṭhikaṅkalam sunikkantaṃ nikkantaṃ nimmaṃsaṃ lohitaṃ makkhitaṃ upasumbheyya.* **English** : A deft butcher or their apprentice would toss them a skeleton scraped clean of flesh and smeared in blood.
- **Pali** : *Taṃ kiṃ maññasi, gahapati,* **English** : What do you think, householder?
- **Pali** : *api nu kho so kukkuro amuṃ aṭṭhikaṅkalam sunikkantaṃ nikkantaṃ nimmaṃsaṃ lohitaṃ makkhitaṃ palehanto jighacchādubbalyaṃ paṭivineyyā*”ti? **English** : Gnawing on such a fleshless skeleton, would that dog still get rid of its hunger?”
- **Pali** : *”No hetam, bhante”. ”Taṃ kissa hetu”?* **English** : ”No, sir. Why not?”
- **Pali** : *”Aduñhi, bhante, aṭṭhikaṅkalam sunikkantaṃ nikkantaṃ nimmaṃsaṃ lohitaṃ makkhitaṃ.* **English** : Because that skeleton is scraped clean of flesh and smeared in blood.
- **Pali** : *Yāvadeva pana so kukkuro kilamathassa vighātassa bhāgī assā*”ti. **English** : That dog will eventually get weary and **frustrated**”.
- **Pali** : *”Evameva kho, gahapati, ariyasāvako iti paṭisañcikkhati:* **English** : “In the same way, a noble disciple reflects :
- **Pali** : *’aṭṭhikaṅkalūpamā kāmā vuttā bhagavatā bahudukkhā bahupāyāsā, ādīnava ettha bhiyyo*’ti. **English** : ’With the simile of a skeleton the Buddha said that sensual pleasures give little gratification and much suffering and distress, and they are all the more full of drawbacks.’

- **Pali** : *Evametam yathābhūtam sammappaññāya disvā yāyam upekkhā nānattā nānattasitā tam abhinivajjetvā, yāyam upekkhā ekattā ekattasitā yattha sabbaso lokāmisūpādānā aparisesā nirujjhanti tamevūpekkham bhāveti.* **English** : Having truly seen this with right understanding, they reject equanimity based on diversity and develop only the equanimity based on unity, where all kinds of grasping to the worldly pleasures of the flesh cease without anything left over.

23.6 Aṅguttara Nikāya 8.14, 2. Mahāvagga (The Great Chapter), Assakhaḷuṅkasutta (A Wild Colt)

- **Pali** : *Puna caparam, bhikkhave, bhikkhū bhikkhum āpattiyā codenti.* **English** : Furthermore, the mendicants accuse a mendicant of an offense.
- **Pali** : *So bhikkhu bhikkhūhi āpattiyā codiyamāno ’nevāham āpannomhi, na panāham āpannomhī’ti so tuṅhībhāvena saṅgham viheṭheti.* **English** : But the accused mendicant neither confesses to the offense nor denies it, but **frustrates** the Saṅgha by staying silent.

23.7 Majjhima Nikāya 100, Middle Discourses, Saṅgārasutta With Saṅgāra

- **Pali** : *Seyyathāpi, bhāradvāja, allam kaṭṭham sasneham udake nikkhattam.* **English** : Suppose there was a green, sappy log, and it was lying in water.
- **Pali** : *Atha puriso āgaccheyya uttarāraṇim ādāya :* **English** : Then a person comes along with a drill-stick, thinking
- **Pali** : *’aggim abhinibbattessāmi, tejo pātukarissāmi’ti.* **English** : to light a fire and produce heat.
- **Pali** : *Tam kim maññasi, bhāradvāja, api nu so puriso amum allam kaṭṭham sasneham udake nikkhattam uttarāraṇim ādāya abhimanthento aggim abhinibbatteyya, tejo pātukareyyā’ti?* **English** : What do you think, Bhāradvāja? By drilling the stick against that green, sappy log lying in water, could they light a fire and produce heat?”
- **Pali** : *’No hidam, bho gotama. Tam kissa hetu?’* **English** : “No, worthy Gotama. Why is that?”
- **Pali** : *Aduñhi, bho gotama, allam kaṭṭham sasneham, tañca pana udake nikkhattam;* **English** : Because it’s a green, sappy log, and it’s lying in the water.
- **Pali** : *yāvadeva ca pana so puriso kilamathassa vighātassa bhāgi assā’ti.* **English** : That person will eventually get weary and **frustrated.**”
- **Pali** : *’Evameva kho, bhāradvāja, ye hi keci samaṇā vā brāhmaṇā vā kāyena ceva citta ca kāmehi avūpakaṭṭhā viharanti, yo ca nesaṁ kamesu kāmacchando kāmasneho kāmamucchā kāmapipāsā kāmapariḷāho so ca ajjhattam na suppahīno hoti na suppaṭippassaddho, opakkamikā cepi te bhonto samaṇabrāhmaṇā dukkhā tibbā kharā kaṭukā vedanā vedayanti, abhabbāva te ṇāṇāya dassanāya anuttarāya sambodhāya. No cepi te bhonto samaṇabrāhmaṇā opakkamikā*

dukkhā tibbā kharā katukā vedanā vedayanti abhabbāva te nāṇāya dassanāya anuttarāya sambodhāya. **English** : "In the same way, there are ascetics and brahmins who don't live withdrawn in body and mind from sensual pleasures. They haven't internally given up or stilled desire, affection, infatuation, thirst, and passion for sensual pleasures. Regardless of whether or not they suffer painful, sharp, severe, acute feelings due to overexertion, they are incapable of knowledge and vision, of supreme awakening.

23.8 Majjhima Nikāya 75, Middle Discourses, Māgaṇḍiyasutta (With Māgaṇḍiya)

- **Pali** : "Seyyathāpi, māgaṇḍiya, jaccandho puriso; **English** : "Māgaṇḍiya, suppose a person was blind from birth.
- **Pali** : *so na passeyya kaṇhasukkāni rūpāni, na passeyya nīlakāni rūpāni, na passeyya pītākāni rūpāni, na passeyya lohitaṅkāni rūpāni, na passeyya mañjīṭṭhakāni rūpāni, na passeyya samavisaṃmāṇi, na passeyya tāraṅkāni rūpāni, na passeyya candimasūriye.* **English** : They couldn't see sights that are dark or bright, or blue, yellow, red, or magenta. They couldn't see even and uneven ground, or the stars, or the moon and sun.
- **Pali** : *Tassa mittāmaccā nāṭisālohitā bhisakkaṃ sallakattaṃ upatthāpeyyuṃ.* **English** : Their friends and colleagues, relatives and kin would get a surgeon to treat them.
- **Pali** : *Tassa so bhisakko sallakatto bhesajjaṃ kareyya.* **English** : The surgeon would make medicine for them,
- **Pali** : *So taṃ bhesajjaṃ āgamma na cakkhūni uppādeyya, na cakkhūni visodheyya.* **English** : but when they used it their eyes were not cured and they still could not see clearly.
- **Pali** : *Taṃ kiṃ maññasi, māgaṇḍiya,* **English** : What do you think, Māgaṇḍiya?
- **Pali** : *nanu so vejjo yāvadeva kilamathassa vighātassa bhāgī assā'ti?* **English** : Wouldn't that doctor just get weary and **frustrated**?"
- **Pali** : "Evaṃ, bho gotama". **English** : "Yes, worthy Gotama".
- **Pali** : "Evameva kho, māgaṇḍiya, ahañce te dhammaṃ deseyyāmi : **English** : "In the same way, suppose I were to teach you the Dhamma, saying :
- **Pali** : 'idantaṃ ārogyaṃ, idantaṃ nibbānaṃ'ti, so tvaṃ ārogyaṃ na jāneyyāsi, nibbānaṃ na passeyyāsi. **English** : 'This is that health, this is that extinguishment.' But you might not know health or see extinguishment,
- **Pali** : *So mamassa kilamatho, sā mamassa vihesā'ti.* **English** : which would be wearying and troublesome for me."

Bhavatu Sabba Mangalam
May all beings be happy

References

Ambalaṅgoḍa Polvattē Buddhādatta. *English-Pali Dictionary*. Motilal Banarsidass Publ., 1989.

TW Rhys Davids and William Stede. *Pali-english dictionary*. Motilal Banarsidass Publ., 1921-1925.